

Using Blackboard for Developing Self Paced Learning on Reading English Comprehension Skills : Short Functional Text for English Learners

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A

What is Blackboard?

One of the platforms for accessing online learning, which has supporting features for online learning.

 Institution Page

 Putri Agustina

 Activity Stream

 Courses

Blackboard
COURSESITES

 Organizations

 Calendar

 Messages

 Grades

How to access a course?

01

Register for CourseSites

About You All fields are required

First Name	Last Name
<input type="text" value="Agus"/>	<input type="text" value="Tina"/>
Email Address	Confirm Email Address
<input type="text" value="agstnaaaa3@gmail.com"/>	<input type="text" value="agstnaaaa3@gmail.com"/>
Country	Registering as
<input type="text" value="Indonesia"/>	<input type="text" value="Student"/>

02

Create an Account

Username (lowercase and numbers only)

Password

Confirm Password

03

Verification

Yes, I agree to the [Terms of Use](#)

Yes, sign me up for emails with exclusive industry insights, upcoming events and webinars, and updates on Blackboard's products and services.

I'm not a robot

reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

Submit

04

Blackboard®

Username

Password

Sign In

[Forgot Password?](#)

[Create an Account](#) [Need Help?](#)

Get a Email@

By Instructor, to invite you to join a courses.

Available to Access

You are can access The Module and after completing the Module, you must to answer in the quiz section.

 QUIZ
Due date: 1/15/21, 12:00 AM

ABOUT THE MODULE

Course Content

INTRODUCTION

Visible to students

LEARNING OUTCOMES

Visible to students

LEARNING PURPOSE

Visible to students

MODULE

INTRODUCTION

Visible to students

Dear my students,

...

14

Welcome to the online lesson (Self Paced Learning) about Short Functional Text. I hope using this online system can help you in learning. The condition for completing this learning is that you must understand the material I provide, and after that you can only do the quiz at the end of the lesson.

Do your best, good luck!

Thank You.

MODULE

LEARNING OUTCOMES

Visible to students

You will be assessed on the following learnings outcomes :

...

1. Describe Functional Text.
2. Describe the four types of Functional Text.
3. Describe the differences between the 4 short functional text.
4. Can practice how to make short functional text

MODULE

LEARNING PURPOSE

Visible to students

1. Students are expected to understand functional text.
2. Students can find out four types of Short Functional Texts.
3. Students can distinguish four Short Functional Texts.
4. Students can create / practice creating four Short Functional Texts at the same time.
5. Can evaluate the ability of Short Functional Texts material in the Quiz section.

ABOUT THE MODULE

Short Functional Text

Visible to students

What is Short Functional Text?

Visible to students

Chapter I : Announcements

Visible to students

What is Announcement text?

Visible to students

MODULE

What is Announcement text?

Visible to students

Announcements are the form of text that is spoken, written, or printed so that other people

know the information that happened or that will happen.

Things that need to be considered in making written announcements are the title or type of event (the title / type of an event), the place, and the person / address that can be contacted).

source: Diah Dedi UBR 2017/2018

MODULE

What is Short Functional Text?

Visible to students

Short functional texts are types of information texts to help the information receivers or readers grasp the information quickly, and that has a specific meaning and function that is commonly used in everyday.

There are some examples of Short Functional Text :

1. Announcement
2. Invitations
3. Notice
4. Letter/E-mails

More discussion about functional text is discussed later. You can click on the table below.

Example of Announcements :

Sample campaign announcement letter

Dear (employee name),

We each have the power to help transform the world. And we can begin right here in Miami, our own community.

It takes all of us working together to create a more educated, prosperous and healthy Miami-Dade, and you are essential to realizing that vision for our community.

United Way has a community plan focused on education, financial stability and health. Education is at the foundation of it all. A good education leads to better jobs, better health, a better quality of life. And for those who need an extra hand, United Way is there to help. When we invest directly in the community care, the money also local and is invested by United Way volunteers - people just like you. Every dollar you give to the United Way community plan - rather than to a specific agency - earns the \$2.58 worth of help through matching grants, in-kind gifts and volunteer time.

Our United Way campaign begins on (date). I am pleased to announce that (name of UWAY) has graciously agreed to be our employee campaign manager. Very soon (he or she) will be announcing special events and ways that you can be a part of this exciting campaign. Last year, our organization raised \$9.1M and I am confident that with your help, this year we can be even more successful and even exceed our goal of \$15M - changing more lives than ever here in Miami-Dade.

I invite you to give your time, your resources, your voice and your talents. Please give generously.

Join me and LIVE UNITED.

Thank you,
(CEO name)

You can open this video for get more explanation about announcement.

<https://youtu.be/qOGHhPLtHQ>

ABOUT THE MODULE

MODULE

SUMMARY : SHORT FUNCTIONAL TEXT

Visible to students

Short Functional Text is to convey something that has a specific purpose and message, according to the type of text used. ...

There are some examples of short functional text :

Announcement :

Announcement is a form of text that can be pronounced, written, or printed so that other people know the information or events that have occurred.

Things that can be considered before making the announcement:

1. Title / type of event
2. date & time
3. place
4. person / address who can be contacted

Invitations :

Invitations are in the form of attending an important activity / event, which needs to be studied before making an invitation.

1. Name
2. Events
3. Time
4. Place
5. Additional messages / information
6. The name of the invitee

Notice :

Notice is short or simple information and can be in the form of information, instruction, or warning to the public. For notice which contains notification addressed to the company.

Letter/E-mails :

This letter is a message, divided into 2 parts, namely Formal and Informal.

Everything is written according to the writing format of each type, so that the recipient / reader knows what the purpose of the text is.

Summary

Visible to students

SUMMARY : SHORT FUNCTIONAL TEXT

Visible to students

ABOUT THE MODULE

QUIZ

Visible to students

After understanding and studying the material above about Short Functional Text, you can do the quiz below, answer it well and correctly, good luck!

QUIZ
Due date: 1/15/21, 11:42 AM
Visible to students

Quiz Content

Question 1

15 points

The following text is for questions 1 and 4.

ANNOUNCEMENT OF PT FAMOUSTEX

The Board of Directors PT Famoustex received a resignation letter on 5th February 2018 from Mrs. Alena Prameswari, an executive director of PT Famoustex. Due to her age, Mrs. Alena Prameswari tendered her resignation from the position of executive director of PT Famoustex. According to the Company Law and other relevant laws and regulations, the resignation of Mrs. Alena Prameswari takes effect on 5th March 2018.

Mrs. Alena Prameswari has confirmed that she has no disagreement with the Board and there is no matter that needs to be brought to the attention of the shareholders of the company. She has also confirmed that she does not have any action or claim, existing or pending, against the company.

The Board fully acknowledges the outstanding contribution of Mrs. Alena Prameswari to the company during her tenure, and would like to express its sincere gratitude to her.

By Order of the Board of Directors

Eko Nugraha
Chairperson

source : Denk-Desk UNBK 2017/2018

What is the objective of the text?

Choose at least one correct answer

- A. To announce the director's registration Correct answer
- B. To show the new position in the company
- C. To inform the new director of the company
- D. To notify the change of the board of directors.
- E. To express gratitude to the former executive director.

Question 3

5 points

Is it true that the text above is a Notice Text?

- True
- False Correct answer

Question 4

5 points

Is it true that the text above is Announcement Text?

- True Correct answer
- False

Question 5

30 points

Create an invitation text with the theme of a birthday celebration!

Students can use the editor to answer

GRADE

Question 1

15 / 15

The following text is for questions 1 and 4.

ANNOUNCEMENT OF PT FAMOUSTEX

The Board of Directors PT Famoustex received a resignation letter on 5th February 2018 from Mrs. Alena Prameswari, an executive director of PT Famoustex. Due to her age, Mrs. Alena Prameswari tendered her resignation from the position of executive director of PT Famoustex. According to the Company Law and other relevant laws and regulations, the resignation of Mrs. Alena Prameswari takes effect on 5th March 2018.

Mrs. Alena Prameswari has confirmed that she has no disagreement with the Board and there is no matter that needs to be brought to the attention of the shareholders of the company. She has also confirmed that she does not have any action or claim, existing or pending, against the company.

The Board fully acknowledges the outstanding contribution of Mrs. Alena Prameswari to the company during her tenure, and would like to express its sincere gratitude to her.

By Order of the Board of Directors

Eko Nugraha
Chairperson

source : Desk-Desk UNBK 2017/2018

What is the objective of the text?

Hide answer choices

- A. To announce the director's registration
- B. To show the new position in the company
- C. To inform the new director of the company
- D. To notify the change of the board of directors.
- E. To express gratitude to the former executive director.

Correct answer

Hide feedback

Feedback

The answer is concluded from the sentence in paragraph one. The Board of Directors PT Famoustex received a resignation letter on 5th February 2018 from Mrs. Alena Prameswari, an executive director of PT Famoustex. The resignation of Mrs. Alena Prameswari takes effect on 5th March 2018. So, the announcement aims to announce the resignation of a director, according to the answer choice (A).

Question

30 / 30

Create an invitation text with the theme of a birthday celebration!

Answer

Michael,

Hi there..

I invite you to my birthday party, hope you join in my celebration.

Date : January, 20 2021
 Time : 07.00 AM
 Place : White Park
 Dress Code : White and Black.

See you later,

Thank you

MODULE QUIZ

Visible to students

Content and Settings

Submissions

1 of 2 SUBMITTED		0 TO GRADE	0 TO POST
Student	Status	Grade	
Alara Dhiafakhri <small>Unopened (late)</small>	No submission	0 / 100 <small>Automatic zero</small>	Posted
Agus Tina <small>Attempted on 1/15/21, 11:42 AM (late)</small>	Complete	55 / 100	Posted

REFERENCE

Intan Pariwara, 2017, Detik – Detik Ujian Nasional Berbasis Komputer, Bahasa Inggris, untuk SMA/MA.

THANKS!

Do you have any questions?

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yourcompany.com

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